

**Identification of isopentenyl transferase (MiaA) target tRNAs in
*Mycobacterium tuberculosis***

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Tuberculosis, caused by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, (Mtb) is one of the oldest diseases associated with mankind. Mtb, an intracellular pathogen, fine tunes its gene expression levels at transcriptional as well as translational level to survive the host immune responses. tRNA modifications provide an avenue to regulate protein synthesis in bacteria by selective up or down regulation of mRNAs with biased cognate codons. Several studies have shown regulation of tRNA modifications under various environmental stresses. N⁶-isopentenyladenosine modification at the 37th position of several tRNAs by isopentenyl transferase (MiaA) is a modification present in bacteria to mammals, which stabilizes codon-anticodon interactions during translation. In addition to increased translation fidelity and speed, i6A modification is essential for the adaptation to stationary phase and virulence in many bacteria. In order to identify tRNA targets of MiaA in Mtb, we analysed the tRNA sequences of Mtb for the A36-A37-A38 motif and identified 8 possible target tRNAs. Modification of the target tRNAs are confirmed by i6A assay providing the substrate dimethylallyl pyrophosphate and recombinant MiaA.